

Group I

PEAL YFV mosquito pools

Source: Endemics Control
Superintendence

- 2,232 mosquitoes
- 753 pools
- 9 YFV RNA+ pools
- 9 YFV Ct available
- PEAL Zones A–C
- 9 YFV genome sequences

Group II

PEAL YFV NP samples

Source: São Paulo Municipal
Health Department

- 37 YFV RNA+
- 25 YFV Ct available
- 37 decomposition stage
- *Alouatta guariba* (n=37)
- PEAL Zones A–C
- 32 YFV genome sequences

Group III

Background NP samples

Source: Centro de Virologia,
Adolfo Lutz Institute

- 53 YFV RNA+
- 50 YFV Ct available
- No decomposition stage
- *Alouatta guariba* (n=49)
- *Callithrix* spp. (n=4)
- Cantareira (PEC) & Mairipora
- 47 YFV genome sequences

Whole genome sequencing

- Targeted multiplex PCR
- Turbo DNase and untargeted SMART-9N

Bioinformatics and QC

- Minimap2, SAMtools, medaka, Tablet
- Kraken2, pluspf viral dbs

Phylogenetic analysis

- NCBI virus db
- MAFFT, Aliview, IqTree v2
- TempEst, BEAST X